

Impact Of Indian Politics In The World (In The Perspective Of USA And Russia)

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Abstract

India's rise to power has led to speculation and expectations about how it will change the global order. On the one hand, India is huge, with more than 1.3 billion people, and on track to become the world's third-largest economy. Yet India still struggles with poverty and other challenges of a developing economy. India is also the largest and most diverse democracy, but hesitates to promote these values abroad. As the United States welcomes and supports India's rise, Americans should better understand Indians' ambitions for themselves and for their role in the Indo-Pacific and on the world stage—ambitions that are still debated within India. In my book, blog posts, and articles, I focus on the live debates in Indian foreign and economic policy shaping India's future course. I also convene the U.S. Relations with South Asia Roundtable Series to address the challenges and opportunities facing the U.S.-India relationship. The research paper explains the India's Political relations with the world politics, particularly with USA and Russia states.

Key Words: India's political arena with USA, India's political arena with Russia

Introduction

India has diplomatic relations with 201 states/dependencies around the globe, having 199 missions and posts operating globally while plans to open new missions in 2020–21 hosted by 11 UN Member States. The Ministry of External Affairs (MEA), also known as the Foreign Ministry, is the government agency responsible for the conduct of foreign relations of India. With the world's third largest military expenditure, second largest armed force, fifth largest economy by GDP nominal rates and third largest economy in terms of purchasing power parity, India is a prominent regional power, a nuclear power, an emerging global power and a potential superpower. India assumes a growing international influence and a prominent voice in global affairs.

As a former British colony, India is a member of the Commonwealth of Nations and continues to maintain relationships with other Commonwealth countries. Since

gaining independence from Britain in 1947, however, India is now classified as a newly industrialised country and has cultivated an extensive network of foreign relations with other states. As a member state of major economies

encompasses Brazil, Russia, China and South Africa, India also exerts a salient influence as the founding member of the Non-Aligned Movement. In recent decades, India has pursued a more expansive foreign policy that encompasses the neighbourhood first policy embodied by SAARC as well as the Look East policy to forge more extensive economic and strategic relationships with other East Asian countries. Moreover, India was one of the founding members of several international organisations—the United Nations, the Asian Development Bank, New Development BRICS Bank, and G-20, widely considered the main economic locus of emerging and developed nations.

Indias Role In Balancing Trade Relations With Westren And Eastren Nations And The Groups

India has also played an important and influential role in other international organisations like East Asia Summit, World Trade Organization, International Monetary Fund (IMF), G8+5 and IBSA Dialogue Forum. India is also a member of the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank and the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation.

Regionally, India is a part of SAARC and BIMSTEC. India has taken part in several UN peacekeeping missions, and as of June 2020, is the fifth-largest troop contributor. India is currently seeking a permanent seat in the UN Security Council, along with the other G4 nations.

India wields enormous influence in global affairs and can be classified as an emerging superpower. The deep impact Russia has on India can be gauged by the words of PM himself. PM said that “Every child in India knows Russia is a friend”. Russia being a time tested friend of India.

Indias Political Relations With Usa U S - India Relations

The U.S.-India strategic partnership is founded on shared values including a commitment to

democracy and upholding the rules-based international system. The United States and India have shared interests in promoting global security, stability, and economic prosperity through trade, investment, and connectivity. President Biden and Prime Minister Modi have held two in person bilateral meetings during which they reaffirmed their commitment to a resilient, rules-based international order that safeguards sovereignty and territorial integrity, upholds democratic values, and

promotes peace and prosperity for all. President Biden and Prime Minister Modi have also participated in multiple engagements of the Quad Leaders mechanism with Japan and Australia. The United States supports India's emergence as a leading global power and a vital partner in efforts to safeguard the Indo-Pacific as a region of peace, stability, and growing prosperity. The strong people-to-people ties between our countries, reflected in the four million-strong Indian American diaspora and vibrant educational exchange between the two countries, are a tremendous source of strength for the strategic partnership. The '2+2 Ministerial Dialogue between the U.S. Secretaries of State and Defence and their Indian counterparts' is the premier recurring dialogue mechanism between the United States and India. The United States hosted the fourth 2+2 Dialogue in April 2022. In addition to the 2+2 Dialogue, the United States and India cooperated in dozens of bilateral dialogues and working groups, which span all aspects of human endeavour, from space and health cooperation to energy and high technology trade. These include the U.S.-India Counterterrorism Joint Working Group, which was established in 2000, as well as the Strategic Clean Energy Partnership, Climate Action and Finance Mobilization Dialogue, Cyber Dialogue, Civil Space Working Group, the Education and Skills Development Working Group, Trade Policy Forum, Defence Policy Group, and Counternarcotics Working Group.

Economic Relations

In 2021, overall U.S.-India bilateral trade in goods and services reached a record \$157 billion. The United States is India's largest trading partner and most important export market. Many U.S. companies view India as a critical market and have expanded their operations there. Likewise, Indian companies seek to increase their presence in U.S. markets and at the end of 2020; Indian investment in the United States totalled \$12.7 billion, supporting over 70,000 American jobs. The nearly 200,000 Indian students in the United States contribute \$7.7 billion annually to the U.S. economy.

International Cooperation

India and the United States cooperate closely at multilateral organizations, including the United Nations, G-20, Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Regional Forum, International Monetary Fund, World Bank,

and World Trade Organization. The United States welcomed India joining the UN Security Council in 2021 for a two-year term and supports a reformed UN Security Council that includes India as a permanent member. India is an ASEAN dialogue partner, an Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development partner, and an observer to the Organization of American States. Together with Australia and Japan, the United States and India convene as the Quad to promote a free and open Indo-Pacific and provide tangible benefits to the region. In June of 2022, the Quad countries concluded recruitment for the inaugural Quad Fellows, an opportunity for 100 students, 25 each from Australia, India, Japan, and the United States, to pursue a master's or doctoral studies in STEM in the United States. India is also one of twelve countries partnering with the United States on the Indo-Pacific Economic Framework for Prosperity (IPEF) to make our economies more connected, resilient, clean, and fair. India is a member of the Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA), at which the United States is a dialogue partner. In 2021, the United States joined the International Solar Alliance headquartered in India, and in 2022 the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) Administrator Samantha Power became Co-chair of the Governing Council of the Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructure (CDRI) where India is a permanent co-chair.

Indias Political Relations With Russia And The East

Nuclear Pact

Russia has inked nuclear pact with India. It has actively supported India with setting up of Kundankulam nuclear power plant and is also supporting in its expansion. This support in the arena of nuclear power is significant because India need to augment its capacity under nuclear power programmed to keep up to its commitment under Paris climate deal.

Kaveri Engine

Russia is actively supporting India with the development of the indigenous Kaveri engine. Kaveri engine will add to India's capacity in defence production.

Make in India is a key programme of the government to develop its manufacturing sector. Russia is actively partnering India in this initiative. India and Russia have signed a landmark deal to jointly manufacture new

generation of light military choppers Kamov 226 under the Make in India. Russia has been constant supporter for India's entry into NSG and APEC. The membership of this premier organization will enhance India's stature.

The structural rigidities have been eliminated with India's membership to MTCR. Russia and India are now planning for Upgradation of the missile system. Brahmos has generated new interests in the world with many countries expressing their desire to acquire Brahmos.

Russia is actively pursuing goal of bringing stability in Afghanistan. It has proposed peace talks as part of its effort. This peace talks with Taliban which is yet to abandon the path of violence is giving legitimacy to Taliban. It is also endorsing the view of good terrorism and bad terrorism. Friendship 2017-military exercise between Pakistan and Russia showed increasing proximity between Russia and Pakistan. There were also talks about the possibility of Russian arm exports to Pakistan...

Traditionally Russia has maintained a neutral position on the issue of conflicts between India and China. In the light of increasing drift between US and Russia, to an extent this multi-vectored policy is adversely affecting India's interests in the region.

Objectives

To understand the political and social stability of India with the world

To maintain the good geo-political relations with the major countries of the world USA and Russia and other major states in the world.

To understand the regional alliances or the groups like ASEAN, BRIC'S, G8, G20 etc, and its merits for India, if it be the member country.

Need Of The Study

To maintain good international relations by India.

For balancing the power between India and the other nations.

The increase in the political stability India increases the role of India's participation in the world politics.

Conclusion

After the Second World War (1945), the United States of America (USA or US in short) emerged as one of the two super powers, the other being the Union of Soviet

Socialist Republics (USSR/ Soviet Union). These countries were militarily and economically so strong as compared to other states that they could project their power to every nook and corner of the world. When India attained independence in 1947, it wanted to have good relations with both the countries. It was widely believed that a natural tie would exist between India and the US since India seemed destined to emerge as the world's largest and Asia's first, fully democratic state. And the US was considered the most powerful and celebrated democracy of the world. So far as the relationship between India and the USSR was concerned, a number of commonalties were easily noticed. But the directions of India's relationships with these two countries took different courses. India is trying to balance the close political relationship with USA and Russia, but in recent decades India has increased its trade interests in USA compare to Russia, due to the changing political stability and in the world.

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